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BETWEEN EARTH OBSERVATION DATA
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APPLICATIONS

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Report assessing back-end driver variability

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List of Acronyms

API	Application Programming Interface
AWS	Amazon Web Services
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CRUD	Create Read Update Delete
CSW	Catalog Service for the Web
EO	Earth Observation
EODC	Earth Observation Data Centre
GDAL	Geospatial Data Abstraction Library
GEE	Google Earth Engine
GIS	Geographical Information System
GRASS	Geographic Resources Analysis Support System
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
NFS	Network File System
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
POC	Proof-Of-Concept
REST	Representational State Transfer
STAC	SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog
TMS	Tile Map Service
UDF	User Defined Function
VITO	Vlaamse Instelling voor Technologisch Onderzoek
WCPS	Web Coverage Processing Service
WCS	Web Coverage Service
WFS	Web Feature Service
WMS	Web Map Service
WMTS	Web Map Tile Service
WWU	Westfälische Wilhelms-Universität

1. Executive Summary

The "Report assessing back-end driver variability" provides an overview of: i) the current state of the back-end drivers, ii) differences and intersections of the back-end architectures, and iii) the challenges the back-end developers faced when implementing the openEO specifications. This information was collected through a questionnaire, which was sent to all back-offices, asking for feedback regarding implementation details of the different openEO endpoints.

It was shown that, even though some back-ends rely on similar systems e.g. for data discovery, the overall system architectures and the faced challenges by the back-ends are quite specific and closely tied to the individual drivers. Furthermore, the questionnaire revealed, that many back-ends already provide infrastructure and systems, that can be interfaced to provide corresponding endpoints to openEO. The back-end developers indicated that the implementation of the job management is the most challenging endpoint, including the execution of UDFs. Finally, the survey demonstrated that the current specification of the openEO API covers all required and expected interfaces to provide EO services to the users.

2. Introduction

Currently, multiple back-ends provide a proof-of-concept by prototypical implementation of openEO. The back-ends rely on different architectures, systems, and interfaces to provide services in the field of EO. Furthermore, most back-ends provide access to diverse data products and processing capabilities. The individual characteristics that arise from these variations have a high impact on the demands and requirements that the back-end drivers have w.r.t to the specification of openEO. On the other side, the implementation of openEO might as well have an impact on the overall system architecture and setup of the back-end systems. In some cases new systems have to be set up to provide certain functionality which is required by openEO, e.g. in the areas of data discovery, process discovery, web services, or job processing.

This report investigates the variability of the various back-ends and aims to analyse the differences, challenges and intersections w.r.t. the implementation of openEO. The general specifications and underlying system architectures of the back-ends are presented in section 4.1. Details of openEO endpoints and functions that have been implemented by the back-ends are outlined in section 4.2. The challenges each back-end faced when implementing openEO (API v0.0.2 as well as v0.3) are listed in section 4.3. The results of a survey, addressing opinions on challenges when implementing openEO at the back-ends is presented in section 4.4. Finally, the conclusion in section 5 gives an deeper insight on the overall variability of the back-end drivers.

This report is based on a questionnaire that was send to the back-end driver developers of the openEO project. The questionnaire was divided into the sections "Back-End Specifications", "Endpoints & Features", "Experience" and "Survey". The responses to all questions can be found in the appendix of this report.

3. Overview of Back-Ends

Table 3.1 lists the currently available openEO back-end drivers and the corresponding organisations. In some cases the driver name refers to a certain software package, e.g. GeoPySpark, and in other cases it refers to a dedicated platform, e.g. Google Earth Engine (GEE). The logic behind this is some drivers serve as proxies for translating openEO-specific requests to the corresponding platforms, e.g. GEE, and other drivers are more closely tied to specific software packages, e.g. GeoPySpark.

Driver	Organisation
GEE	WWU Münster
GeoPySpark	VITO
GRASS GIS	mundialis
OpenShift	EODC
R	WWU Münster
Sentinel Hub	Sinergise
WC(P)S	EURAC Research

Table 3.1: Back-ends included in this report.

4. Back-End Driver Variability

4.1. General Back-End Specifications

This section highlights the differences of general system architectures and software packages used by the back-ends of openEO. As shown in Figure 4.1, the division between file-based, mid-level and high-level back-ends implementing openEO is even. File-based back-ends, provide interfaces or direct accesses to unprocessed Copernicus data and file access via POSIX using e.g. virtual machines, or Representational State Transfer (REST) interfaces. The mid-level back-ends, offer access to their data products using software systems that can be combined with low-level file-based access. The third group, high-level back-ends, are only accessible through API calls. The back-ends had the possibility to classify themselves into multiple categories.

Figure 4.1: Categories of back-ends.

Besides the core software packages or platforms on which the back-end drivers are relying, various software packages or services were used to provide the specified openEO functionality. For sharing geo-spatial data using Web Coverage Service (WCS), Web Map Service (WMS) and Web Coverage Processing Service (WCPS) interfaces are used, some back-ends for example did or plan to setup GeoServer. Further complementing software packages and technologies are:

- MapServer
- OpenSearch
- GeoServer
- PyCSW
- Spark

Various programming languages, libraries and platforms are utilised by the back-end developers. Primarily, Python, using the Flask micro framework, and node.js (JavaScript) to provide REST endpoints of openEO. Furthermore, R with plumber is used by the R-back-end and Java it utilised by EURAC.

Figure 4.2: Programming languages / frameworks used to implement openEO endpoints.

Multiple back-ends already provide a public endpoint to access prototypical implementations of openEO. The URLs for the public endpoints are listed in the following:

- <http://giv-project8.uni-muenster.de>
- <https://openeo.eodc.eu>
- <http://openeo.vgt.vito.be/openeo>
- http://saocompute.eurac.edu/openEO_WCPS_Driver/
- <http://openeo.mundialis.de:5000/processes>

4.2. Endpoints & Features

This section investigates the implementation of the various endpoints and features, specified by the openEO Core API, and highlights the variability between the different back-ends.

4.2.1. EO Data Discovery

The EO data discovery service describes which data-sets and image collections are available at the back-end. Therefore, the discovery functionality enables the user to find available products, details of products and metadata, i.e. bands or extents, and provides identifiers that can be used for referencing the products in the process graph of a job for applying operations and filters.

Products that are available at the back-ends are shown in Figure 4.3. Many back-ends provide Sentinel-2 data. Other available products include Sentinel 1 and 3, Landsat 4-8, MODIS as well as pre-processed Landsat 7 (Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)) data. Google Earth Engine is an exception as it provides access to more than 548 products therefore is excluded from the Figure.

D14: Back-end driver variability

Figure 4.3: Products hosted at the back-ends (the products are aggregated, including processed and spatial-constrained products).

Data discovery is already implemented in some of the back-ends. The endpoint often relies on existing meta-data services and standards like Catalog Service for the Web (CSW) or GeoNetwork. Some of the back-end providers are considering to implement a [SpatioTemporal Asset Catalog \(STAC\)](#). Details on the current state of data discovery, at the individual back-ends, is provided in the following:

GEE The GEE back-end does not yet implement data discovery.

GeoPySpark A data discovery endpoint was not implemented yet since VITO currently has a limited list of available layers.

GRASS GIS A data discovery endpoint is currently implemented for GRASS GIS, that enables to query available raster, vector and raster-collection data from the GRASS GIS database.

OpenShift EODC implemented an abstraction layer on-top of its existing CSW interface to return metadata in the schema defined by openEO.

R The R back-end does not yet implement data discovery.

Sentinel Hub Sentinel-Hub is currently using a OpenSearch interface to provide the openEO data discovery endpoint, but is considering to implement a STAC interface.

WC(P)S EURAC is using GeoNetwork with it's internal API's for data discovery. EURAC is considering STAC for future implementations.

4.2.2. Process Discovery

The process discovery enables to retrieve available processes provided by the corresponding back-ends. The returned process records are specifying the input parameters, the return type, as well as possible errors, and exceptions. A process is an operation or filter that performs a specific task, using a set of parameters, and is applied on data products, or on the output of another process node.

All back-ends provide at least a prototypical process discovery by querying the process databases of their respective back-ends or implementing stand-alone services for process discovery. In the following details on the individual implementations are presented:

GEE The process discovery of the GEE back-end automatically generates the process descriptions from the GEE process implementations.

GeoPySpark VITO has implemented a Flask endpoint, that is separated from the GeoPySpark driver, which implements process discovery.

GRASS GIS The GRASS GIS driver uses the actinia REST API, which supports the definition of process chains, in which any number of GRASS GIS modules can be defined as well as their data exchange.

OpenShift The process discovery at EODC is implemented using a process registry, running as an independent Flask micro service, and is backed by a PostgreSQL database.

R The R back-end is parsing and mapping the processing graphs onto the back-ends implementation of the processes. The processing is then done by invoking the function stack of nested calls.

Sentinel Hub Sentinel Hub has a prototypical implementation of the data discovery, returning JSON description of processes from a node.js back-end. In the future the processes will be separated into their own source files (one file per process).

WC(P)S EURAC provides processes corresponding to the Use Case 1 of the Proof-Of-Concept via their process discovery. In the future all functionality specified by WCPS will be provided.

Furthermore, most of the back-ends already provide processes that were needed for the Proof-Of-Concept (POC). Some back-ends extended or plan to extend their process catalogue with advanced functionality or back-end specific operations. The GRASS GIS for example includes over 500 processing modules, i.e. when defining a process for openEO these modules are employed through an actinia process chain. A selection of available processes that were stated by the back-end providers are shown in Table 4.1.

Filters	Aggregations	Operations
Bounding Box Date Range Bands	Min Time Max Time Mean Time Median Time Sum Time First Time Last Time Time Reducer Zonal statistics	NDVI Stretch Colors Raster Export

Table 4.3: A selection of available processes supported by the various openEO back-ends.

4.2.3. Job Management

The job management service organises and manages jobs that run processes on the back-ends. Jobs can be processes synchronously and asynchronously. The job management service is, among others, responsible for parsing the process graph, monitoring the processing of the jobs and returning information about the job to the users. Furthermore, the job management keeps track of credits contingents used while processing.

The job management service is one the most challenging endpoints to implement, since it requires parsing the process graphs to single executable processing nodes and solutions for job queuing, distribution, monitoring and execution handling. Most of the back-ends rely on software packages that provide most of the required functionality, but nevertheless need to adapt or extend the provided interfaces to serve openEO requests. In the following the current state of job management at the individual back-ends is presented:

GEE The GEE back-end translates openEO requests into GEE JavaScript API requests and triggers the processing on the GEE cloud-infrastructure.

GeoPySpark Process graphs are mapped into (GeoPy)Spark jobs, and processed in a distributed manner. The mapping to Spark is straightforward, since it already supports all the basic concepts that are required by openEO.

GRASS GIS The openEO GRASS GIS driver uses the appropriate actinia REST API endpoints to queue and manage jobs. The actinia REST framework supports asynchronous and synchronous processing and therefore provides a job queue to manage GRASS GIS module calls.

R The R back-end is parsing and mapping the processing graphs onto the back-ends implementation of the processes. The processing is done by invoking the function stack of nested calls.

OpenShift The EODC driver deploys each job as a pod (container), running in the OpenShift/Kubernetes environment. Each pod contains all functionality for accessing the data storage and apply iterative processes on the data. The parameters for the processes are passed to the pods and the processes itself are implemented using Geospatial Data Abstraction Library (GDAL) pixel functions.

Sentinel Hub The Sentinel Hub driver plans to forward the openEO requests to the Sentinel Hub platform. Therefore the Sentinel Hub driver will translate openEO process definitions into Sentinel Hub processing scripts.

WC(P)S At EURAC, an internal database persistently stores jobs and executes them using WCPS.

Currently none of the back-ends have implemented user credits or a billing service. Nevertheless, multiple systems are planning to log run time processing information, to be able to calculate credits used by the user. The following concepts were stated:

- EODC plans to retrieve run time statistics like Central Processing Unit (CPU) or memory usage from to the metrics exporter of the running pods in OpenShift.
- GRASS GIS will keep track of the processing time of each computational process as well as the size of the user specific data.
- Sentinel Hub has existing auditing and logging mechanisms and will keep track and log users requests with the API Key and/or OAuth session identifiers.
- VITO plans to run batch jobs as separate processes, and record the actual CPU and memory usage.

4.2.4. File Management

The file management service organises and manages user-uploaded files. Therefore, users are able to download and upload files to their private work space and reference the uploaded files in process graphs (e.g. an user-uploaded polygon). Furthermore, the results of the processed jobs can be downloaded via the file management service.

Some of the back-ends have implemented file management so far, while other back-ends have developed solid plans on how to implement the file management at their back-ends. The current state is shown in the following:

- GEE** File management is currently implemented as a node.js file service, which is not fully integrated into the GEE API. Later it should use the native GEE functionality to store user files in Google Cloud Storage buckets.
- GeoPySpark** At VITO file management is not yet implemented. Currently two solutions are considered. Either setting up an Object Storage solution, or let users use their shared folders that are already part of the PROBA-V MEP.
- GRASS GIS** The GRASS GIS driver uses the GRASS GIS database to store user specific geo-data. The actinia REST API allows the import of any online available geo-data source into the GRASS GIS database. Geo-data can be raster images, vector feature collections or raster collections.
- R** The R back-end provides up- and download functionality as it was specified in API v0.0.2. Data is available in the Docker shared volume.
- OpenShift** User file management is not yet implemented at the EODC back-end. The data of processed jobs is saved on a Network File System (NFS) server that was set up for the openEO project. In the future, the users will have direct access to their private spaces on the EODC storage server.
- Sentinel Hub** At Sentinel Hub the file management is not implemented yet. Nevertheless they plan to use a cloud database for structured data about users and source code and Amazon Web Services (AWS) S3 object storage for large files
- WC(P)S** At EURAC, file management is currently not planned.

4.2.5. UDF Runtime Discovery

The UDF run time discovery allows exploring programming languages and run-time environments that are available at the back-ends to execute user-defined functions. UDFs allow to upload custom code and have it executed e.g. for every pixel of a scene, allowing custom calculations on server-side data.

The implementation of UDFs is very challenging since it allows executing arbitrary code at the back-ends. Therefore, most of the back-end developers are currently still evaluation possible solution on how to realise UDFs and UDF run time discovery at their back-ends. A prototypical implementation of UDFs is currently only available at the GeoPySpark back-end. The overall state of UDF implementation is presented in the following:

- GEE** GEE is currently not supporting UDFs. Nevertheless, depending of the state of the openEO project, GEE will consider implementing UDFs.
- GeoPySpark** Python UDF's can be evaluated directly, since Spark already supports executing arbitrary Python functions. Providing other languages like R may be more challenging as the execution might impair the performance.
- GRASS GIS** At the GRASS GIS back-end UDFs will run as part of an actinia process chain. A single actinia node is realised as a docker container.
- OpenShift** At EODC UDFs will be wrapped and deployed in Docker containers, that run in OpenShift and can be integrated into existing processing work flows.
- R** The R back-end plans to convert data into appropriate data chunks, serialises them into JSON and send the data chunks to a UDF web service. The service will be written in R and provided as a Docker container, due to being a REST-service .
- Sentinel Hub** Sentinel Hub plans to support JavaScript UDFs, which will be embedded into the Sentinel Hub processing scripts on the fly.
- WC(P)S** EURAC is currently looking into several technologies for implementing UDFs including setups defined by the Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) Testbed 13/14 specifications.

4.2.6. Web Service Management

The web service management provides on-demand access to data and job results hosted at the back-ends, using web service protocols like WCS, WMS or Web Map Tile Service (WMTS). The endpoint specifies Create Read Update Delete (CRUD) operations for web services and enables to subscribe to events, e.g. when an execution update occurs. The supported services types are determined by the particular back-ends and can be requested by the user, using the "/service_types" endpoint.

Some back-ends already provide web services like XYZ, WCS or Tile Map Service (TMS) and other back-ends plan to setup server like GeoServer or MapServer to provide web services. The current state of the web service management implementations include:

- GEE** GEE provides tiled web maps using a XYZ service.
- GeoPySpark** GeoPyspark already supports TMS, but this standard has no support for time series. Hence VITO is looking into supporting WMTS.

- GRASS GIS** GRASS GIS is currently not supporting interactive web services.
- OpenShift** EODC plans to setup a GeoServer for sharing geo spatial data, providing WCS, WMS, Web Feature Service (WFS). The server will be deployed on OpenShift either for each web service publish request or as one instance, providing restricted views on the user data space.
- R** The R back-end plans to setup a MapServer for providing access to the processed jobs data. MapServer config files will be created by calling the respective /service endpoints.
- Sentinel Hub** Sentinel Hub created a simple node.js OGC web service which serves as an openEO-aware proxy to the equivalent Sentinel Hub services
- WC(P)S** EURAC provides web services using GeoServer and rasdaman.

4.2.7. Authentication

The authentication service enables to secure certain endpoints and provides mechanisms to request authentication tokens to provide access to the API functionality. In the openEO API v0.3 specification two approaches are proposed. The first one uses HTTP basic authentication (Figure 4.4), by sending the base-64 encrypted credentials and retrieving a bearer token that is used for further API requests. The second method implements the OpenID Connect (OIDC) 1.0 specification, that provides an identity layer on top of the OAuth 2.0 protocol.

Figure 4.4: Authentication methods currently implemented by the back-ends.

As shown in Figure 4.4, half of the back-ends have implemented authentication using basic/bearer authentication or OIDC. Nevertheless most of the back-end have an existing authentication system, that can be connected to the openEO authentication interface. The overall current state of authentication includes:

- GEE** GEE is using bearer tokens, that are generated after authentication via a Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP) basic token as defined by the API 0.0.2 specification. The GEE driver will in the future align with the openEO API 0.3 by using the GEE OAuth and service accounts.
- GeoPySpark** VITO has not integrated authentication yet, but has an existing solution, to provide an endpoint for authentication. Nevertheless, VITO prefers to offer anonymous usage of openEO until a first version of openEO is available.
- GRASS GIS** User authentication is currently not supported by the openEO GRASS GIS driver. In the future basic/bearer authentication will be used, since the actinia REST framework has a user management system, that is based on basic HTTP authentication.
- OpenShift** Authentication at EODC is implemented using basic authentication and bearer tokens. Furthermore, OpenID Connect authentication is currently implemented, using an external KeyCloak server hosted at EODC.
- R** The R back-end currently uses basic/bearer authentication.
- Sentinel Hub** Sentinel Hub did not yet implement authentication in their driver. Nevertheless, an OAuth-2.0 authentication mechanism is available and will be used to realise authentication.
- WC(P)S** Authentication is not yet implemented at EURAC.

4.3. Challenges & Experience

The majority of back-end developers faced challenges when implementing the openEO API. Particularly, because the requirements, risen by the openEO specification, influenced the overall system architecture at the back-ends, as shown in Figure 4.5. New systems had to be deployed, or existing solutions to be adapted, to provide functionality, that at some back-ends were not existent beforehand. Some major changes to existing systems architectures are listed following:

- The openEO specification required to change specific parts of the GRASS GIS and actinia back-end.

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- At EODC an OpenShift cluster was setup to enable providing the openEO services and job processing.
- GeoPySpark was chosen, instead of plain GeoTrellis by VITO to provide support of UDFs.
- The R back-end incorporated Docker and containerised some of the functionality. Furthermore, some the web services endpoint requires the setup of MapServer.

Figure 4.5: Did the implementation of the openEO influence your overall system setup?

Further challenges that the driver developers were facing when starting to implement the openEO endpoints at their back-ends include:

GEE The GEE developers faced some problems with the openEO API v0.0.2, e.g. insufficient error handling, which was solved with the API v0.3. Furthermore, some information for data discovery is not available at GEE and some processes in GEE do not match the process definitions of openEO (e.g. missing `total_count` and `valid_count` in `zonal_statistics`).

GeoPySpark The fast (pre-)viewing of process graph results through TMS/WMTS was one of the biggest challenges, when implementing the GeoPySpark driver.

GRASS The biggest challenge for the GRASS GIS driver was the conversion of the process graphs into actina REST API process chains, as well as the support for UDFs.

R The R back-end faced challenges, when implementing data management for UDFs, e.g. tiling strategies, or the creation of subsets and slices. Since the R back-end is intended to be a test system, optimising the system performance is challenging as well.

OpenShift A major challenge for EODC was the implementation of job processing and data management, since the data hosted at EODC (level 1c), needs to be extracted, pre-processed and integrated in an iterative processing approach. Therefore, each job has to be deployed in a pod (container) with access to the EODC storage and the private storage of the users. Since each Sentinel product hosted at EODC has another file structure, data extractors had to be implemented for each product.

Sentinel Hub The major challenges that occurred when implementing a driver for Sentinel Hub:

- A major challenge was the need to have a stateful server, with storage of user data.
- Another difficult aspect was the need to execute arbitrary flows, since the Sentinel Hub platform has a more rigid order of execution (filter scenes / create time series / evaluate algorithm on each pixel).
- The interface for retrieving data from the service was a bit ambiguous non-trivial. WCS / WMS / TMS return binary encoded rasters (images), with encoding typically specified by the client at the point of retrieval. openEO deals primarily with measured physical values, and does not clearly define the type of encoding of the result into the output image.

As already stated, the implementation of the job management service (including UDFs) was one of the most challenging tasks for the back-ends. The implementation of web service management, including the provision of WCS / WMS / TMS interfaces were considered to be challenging by many back-ends. Furthermore, the download of job results and the user file upload was mentioned to be difficult to implement.

Most of the back-end developers, as can be seen in Figure 4.6, did not yet switch to v0.3 of the openEO API specification. Nevertheless, many are planning to start the transition to v0.3 soon. The back-ends are considering to implement the following features:

GEE Switch to API v0.3 is due.

GeoPySpark Focus is on viewing services (WMTS) and batch processes.

GRASS The user content endpoints, i.e. user can upload own scripts, data, files and download computed results.

OpenShift Upgrade of the current job processing to match the requirements of the openEO v0.3 API specifications.

R Accessing the job log over web socket (job/<job_id>subscribe) and implement the changes coming with API v0.3.

Sentinel Hub Support for long-running jobs.

WC(P)S Extending the data discovery service.

Figure 4.6: Do you already start to implement v0.3.0 of the openEO API specification?

4.4. Survey

A survey was conducted, aiming to measure the variability in perception w.r.t. the subjective perception on openEO and the challenges implementing the API specification. Five questions on the implementation of openEO were asked, using a Likert scale ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree.

As shown in Figure 4.7, the range of opinions relating to the simplicity of implementing openEO at the back-end was diversified, meaning that for some back-end developer the implementation was perceived simpler than for others. This can be related to the availability of functionality provided by existing software systems, as can be concluded from the second question. The back-end developers have the opinion, that the openEO v0.3 specifications defines all functions and capabilities they expect it to have. The API design therefore is suitable to represent the functional bandwidth of all back-ends. The opinion on the simplicity of installing the respective developed drivers at other back-ends, were either strongly agreeing or strongly disagreeing and may relate to how specific the drivers are tied to the underlying software systems or platforms of the drivers. Most of the back-end driver developers state that they will support all the endpoints and functionality defined by the openEO v0.3 API specification.

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Figure 4.7: Results of the survey.

5. Conclusions

The results of this report show that the variability between the back-end provider is quite significant. The back-ends are relying on software packages, technologies, data products which are very diversified. This challenge is shared by the back-end driver developers when implementing the interfaces of openEO at their back-ends. The drivers themselves range from being closely tied to the respective platforms to more general applicability. Nevertheless, many areas show intersections in used technologies, like the usage of GeoServer for web services or the planned implementation of STAC for data discovery. Furthermore, results show that most of the endpoints specified by the openEO specification are already implemented or are planned by the back-end driver developers. Finally, many back-end provider have existing infrastructure for various endpoints that can be used for interfacing openEO endpoints.

The most challenging endpoint to implement for the back-end driver developers is the job management, including the execution of UDFs. This finding is coherent, since the endpoint has the greatest demands on the system architectures and interfaces as well as the greatest complexity in feasibility. Furthermore, the web service endpoint was considered by many back-ends as challenging, since it often requires the setup of an external service, like GeoServer or MapServer.

The conducted survey showed the overall satisfaction of the back-end driver developers with the specification of the openEO API. Beyond this, it was highlighted that the simplicity of im-

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plementing openEO at the back-end was strongly diversified, which could be correlated to the availability of required functionality at the back-end.

Appendices

A. Answers To Questionnaire

A.1. GEE Back-End / WWU

Name of your company

WWU Münster

What software package is the back-end driver targeting (e.g. WCPS, GeoPySpark, ...)?

Google Earth Engine

What is the category of the back-end (file-based, mid-level, high-level)?

high-level

Are other back-end systems used to serve openEO requests and enable processing (e.g. rasdaman, Spark, CSW, GeoNetwork, ...)?

Which technologies are used to realize the openEO API endpoints (e.g. Python/flask, node.js/express, ...)?

node.js, restify, Google Earth Engine JS API, nedb

Which data products (e.g. Sentinel-2) are available at the back-end?

548 products, e.g. MODIS, Sentinel 1/2/3, Landsat 1/2/3/4/5/7/8

Do you have a public endpoint (if yes: URL)?

<http://giv-project8.uni-muenster.de>

Other comments...

Mostly a proxy for GEE.

Do you already start to implement v0.3.0 of the openEO API specification?

Yes

Which technologies did/will you use to implement EO data discovery?

None yet

What processes (e.g. NDVI) does your back-end offer and how did/will you implement process discovery?

"Processes: zonal_statistics, ndvi, filter_bands, filter_bbox, filter_daterange, count_time, max_time, min_time, mean_time, median_time, sum_time, last_time, first_time, stretch_colors

Process discovery: Automatically generated from process implementations."

How did/will you realize processing jobs at your back-end?

openEO requests are translated into GEE JS API requests and processed on the GEE cloud-infrastructure. Details on processing by GEE are unknown.

How did/will you implement UDFs (e.g. using Docker containers)?

Not planned yet as GEE doesn't support UDFs natively, but would be interested to implement it if our approach is satisfying and secure.

How did/will you realize interactive web services (e.g. WMS, TMS)?

Tiled web map (XYZ) is implemented, no other web service support planned yet.

How did/will you implement user file management and user storage?

Currently implemented as node.js file service, which is not fully integrated into the GEE API. Later it should use the native GEE functionality to store user files in Google Cloud Storage buckets.

Do you already possess user authentication at the back-end? How did/will you realize openEO endpoints for user accounts and authentication?

Yes, currently proprietary Bearer Token are generated after authentication via HTTP Basic as defined by API 0.0.2. Will probably be changed in the future to align with API 0.3 and the GEE OAuth implementation and Service Accounts.

Do you have an existing solution for user credits and billing. How did/will you realize billing?

No, GEE is free.

What is the next endpoint that you will implement at your back-end?

Not planned yet, most endpoints are implemented. Switch to API v0.3 is due.

Other comments...

Did you experience any challenges when when implementing the openEO API at your back-end?

API v0.0.2 had some problems that are solved by API v0.3, e.g. insufficient error handling. Some information for data discovery are not available in GEE. Some processes in GEE do not match our process definitions, e.g. missing total_count and valid_count in zonal_statistics. Web services properties are not well defined, e.g. how do I get/define the layer names in a WMS.

Did the implementation of the openEO specification influence your overall system setup (if yes, how)?

No.

What was the most challenging endpoint to implement yet?

GET /jobs/job_id/download and PUT /users/user_id/files/path

Did you face any challenges when switching from openEO API v0.0.2 to openEO API v0.3.0?

Just starting with API 0.3, but comprehensive process discovery and OIDC authentication will be challenges.

Do you have any other comments or experiences implementing the openEO API, you want to share?

A.2. GeoPySpark / VITO

Name of your company

VITO

What software package is the back-end driver targeting (e.g. WCPS, GeoPySpark, ...)?

GeoPySpark

What is the category of the back-end (file-based, mid-level, high-level)?

mid-level, high-level

Are other back-end systems used to serve openEO requests and enable processing (e.g. rasdaman, Spark, CSW, GeoNetwork, ...)?

Spark is used for distributed processing.

Which technologies are used to realize the openEO API endpoints (e.g. Python/flask, node.js/express, ...)?

Python/flask

Which data products (e.g. Sentinel-2) are available at the back-end?

Sentinel-2, Proba-V, Copernicus Global Land products

Do you have a public endpoint (if yes: URL)?

<http://openeo.vgt.vito.be/openeo>

Other comments...

The Flask implementation of OpenEO and process graph deserialization has been split of into a separate repository, which is not dependent on GeoPySpark. This would allow other backend implementors that use Python to get going more easily.

Do you already start to implement v0.3.0 of the openEO API specification?

Yes

Which technologies did/will you use to implement EO data discovery?

Still open, we just have a (limited) list of layers for the moment.

What processes (e.g. NDVI) does your back-end offer and how did/will you implement process discovery?

We implement the OpenEO process discovery API:<http://openeo.vgt.vito.be/openeo/processes>

How did/will you realize processing jobs at your back-end?

Process graphs are mapped into (geopy)spark jobs, and processed in a distributed manner. The mapping to spark is fairly easy, as it already supports all the basic concepts that are needed.

How did/will you implement UDFs (e.g. using Docker containers)?

Python UDF's can be evaluated directly, as Spark already supports executing arbitrary Python functions. Other languages (R) may be less straightforward to support without incurring a performance hit. Supporting Docker is currently not planned.

How did/will you realize interactive web services (e.g. WMS, TMS)?

GeoPyspark already supports TMS, but this standard has no support for time series. Hence we are looking into supporting WMTS.

How did/will you implement user file management and user storage?

Not yet foreseen. Setting up an Object Storage solution might be the most straightforward approach, or else we might let users use their shared folders that are already part of the PROBA-V MEP, which are also accessible over FTP.

Do you already possess user authentication at the back-end? How did/will you realize openEO endpoints for user accounts and authentication?

We have some existing solutions, but nothing integrated with OpenEO yet. I'd rather offer anonymous usage of OpenEO until we have something viable. No, no idea's yet. For batch jobs, we might be able to run them as separate processes, and record actual CPU and Memory usage.

Do you have an existing solution for user credits and billing. How did/will you realize billing?

No, no idea's yet. For batch jobs, we might be able to run them as separate processes, and record actual CPU and Memory usage.

What is the next endpoint that you will implement at your back-end?

Focus is on viewing services (WMTS), batch processes are probably next.

Other comments...

Did you experience any challenges when when implementing the openEO API at your back-end?

Fast (pre-)viewing of process graph results through TMS/WMTS is probably the biggest challenge. A readily available test of the API for conformance would also have helped.

Did the implementation of the openEO specification influence your overall system setup (if yes, how)?

The need to support Python UDF's made me choose GeoPySpark (Python) instead of plain Geotrellis (Scala), but this was not a big issue.

What was the most challenging endpoint to implement yet?

Viewing (TMS)

Did you face any challenges when switching from openEO API v0.0.2 to openEO API v0.3.0?

No

Do you have any other comments or experiences implementing the openEO API, you want to share?

No

A.3. GRASS GIS / mundialis

Name of your company

mundialis GmbH & Co. KG

What software package is the back-end driver targeting (e.g. WCPS, GeoPySpark, ...)?

GRASS GIS with actinia REST API

What is the category of the back-end (file-based, mid-level, high-level)?

file-based, mid-level

Are other back-end systems used to serve openEO requests and enable processing (e.g. rasdaman, Spark, CSW, GeoNetwork, ...)?

The actinia REST API is used to start GRASS GIS processes

Which technologies are used to realize the openEO API endpoints (e.g. Python/flask, node.js/express, ...)?

Python Flask-RESTful

Which data products (e.g. Sentinel-2) are available at the back-end?

Landsat 4 - 8, Sentinel-2

Do you have a public endpoint (if yes: URL)?

- <http://openeo.mundialis.de:5000/capabilities>
- <http://openeo.mundialis.de:5000/data>
- <http://openeo.mundialis.de:5000/processes>

Other comments... n/a

Do you already start to implement v0.3.0 of the openEO API specification?

No

Which technologies did/will you use to implement EO data discovery?

We implement a GRASS GIS driver, i.e. it supports raster, vector and raster-collection (aka STRDS in GRASS GIS) data from the GRASS GIS database which will be visible with unique names in the data discovery endpoint requests.

What processes (e.g. NDVI) does your back-end offer and how did/will you implement process discovery?

GRASS GIS provides over 500 processing modules. The actinia REST API that is used to access the GRASS GIS backend supports the definition of process chains, in which any number of GRASS GIS modules can be defined and their data exchange. The OpenEO GRASS GIS driver supports several processes that includes:

- Raster export
- Bounding box filter
- Datarange filter
- NDVI
- Time reducer
- Zonal statistics

Each process is a actinia process chain and must be implemented individually.

How did/will you realize processing jobs at your back-end?

The actinia REST framework supports asynchronous and synchronous processing and therefore provides a job queue to manage GRASS GIS module calls and actinia process chain

execution. The OpenEO GRASS GIS driver uses the appropriate actinia endpoints to enqueue and manage jobs.

How did/will you implement UDFs (e.g. using Docker containers)?

UDF will be run as part of an actinia process chain. A single actinia node is realized as a docker container.

How did/will you realize interactive web services (e.g. WMS, TMS)?

We do not support interactive web services so far.

How did/will you implement user file management and user storage?

The OpenEO GRASS GIS driver uses the GRASS GIS database to store user specific geo-data. The actinia REST API allows the import of any online available geo-data source into the GRASS GIS database. Geo-data can be raster images, vector feature collections or raster collections.

Do you already possess user authentication at the back-end? How did/will you realize openEO endpoints for user accounts and authentication?

We do not support user authentication at the moment in the openEO GRASS GIS driver. We will use basic authentication for user accounts in the backend, since the actinia REST framework has a user management system and uses basic HTTP authentication.

Do you have an existing solution for user credits and billing. How did/will you realize billing?

We will log the processing time of each computational process as well as the size of the user specific data. So far we have no clear idea how a credit and billing system should look like.

What is the next endpoint that you will implement at your back-end?

The user content endpoints, i.e. user can upload own scripts, data, files and download computed results.

Other comments...

n/a

Did you experience any challenges when when implementing the openEO API at your back-end?

The biggest challenge is the conversion of the process graph into actinia REST API process chains and the UDF support.

Did the implementation of the openEO specification influence your overall system setup (if yes, how)?

The openEO specification required to change specific parts of the GRASS GIS and actinia backend.

What was the most challenging endpoint to implement yet?

The jobs endpoint was and is most challenging. We are not able to support the WMS or WCS interfaces.

Did you face any challenges when switching from openEO API v0.0.2 to openEO API v0.3.0?

We switch from 0.1 to 0.3 and face challenges in the user and job management.

Do you have any other comments or experiences implementing the openEO API, you

want to share?

n/a

A.4. OpenShift / EODC

Name of your company

EODC

What software package is the back-end driver targeting (e.g. WCPS, GeoPySpark, ...)?

OpenShift

What is the category of the back-end (file-based, mid-level, high-level)?

file-based

Are other back-end systems used to serve openEO requests and enable processing (e.g. rasdaman, Spark, CSW, GeoNetwork, ...)?

CSW

Which technologies are used to realize the openEO API endpoints (e.g. Python/flask, node.js/express, ...)?

Python/flask

Which data products (e.g. Sentinel-2) are available at the back-end?

Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2, Sentinel-3

Do you have a public endpoint (if yes: URL)?

<https://openeo.eodc.eu>

Other comments...

Do you already start to implement v0.3.0 of the openEO API specification?

Yes

Which technologies did/will you use to implement EO data discovery?

Metadata is saved and served by a pycsw server (Python implementation of the OGC CSW server). The openEO data discovery is implementing on a layer on top of the pycsw server interfaces. The CSW responses are filtered to serve the metadata according to the openEO v0.3 specification.

What processes (e.g. NDVI) does your back-end offer and how did/will you implement process discovery?

Currently, available processes, that can be applied are: filters on date, time, bands, NDVI, min-time and max-time. The process discovery is implemented using a process registry, running as an independent micro service, backed by a PostgreSQL database.

How did/will you realize processing jobs at your back-end?

Jobs are processed by deploying each job as a pod (container), running in the OpenShift/Kubernetes environment. Each pod contains all functionalities for accessing the EODC data storage and apply iterative processes on the data. The parameters for the processes are passed to the pods and the processes itself are implemented using GDAL pixel functions.

How did/will you implement UDFs (e.g. using Docker containers)?

UDFs will be, same as the regular job processing, implemented using Pods, running in OpenShift and the user-defined scripts will be linked in the GDAL pixel functions/.vrt files. Therefore, in the first stage the back-end will only support Python UDFs.

How did/will you realize interactive web services (e.g. WMS, TMS)?

It is planned to setup a server for sharing geospatial data, based on GeoServer, providing WCS, WMS, WFS. The server will be deployed on OpenShift either for each web service publish request or as one server, providing restricted views on the user data space.

How did/will you implement user file management and user storage?

Currently, data, that is processed by the users, is saved on a NFS server that was exclusive set up for the openEO project. User file-upload is not implemented yet. In the future, the users will have direct access to their private spaces on the EODC storage server.

Do you already possess user authentication at the back-end? How did/will you realize openEO endpoints for user accounts and authentication?

Authentication is implemented using basic authentication and bearer tokens. Furthermore, OpenID Connect authentication/authorization and user management is currently implemented, by accessing an external KeyCloak instance hosted at EODC.

Do you have an existing solution for user credits and billing. How did/will you realize billing?

Not yet implemented. When implemented, we will create a new billing system that is connected to our user and private space management. The billing will be dependent on the metrics measured and sampled from the running job pods.

What is the next endpoint that you will implement at your back-end?

The upgrade of the current job processing to match the requirements of the openEO v0.3 API specifications.

Other comments...

Did you experience any challenges when when implementing the openEO API at your back-end?

A system for container deployment and management as well for job processing had to be set up at EODC. We decided to use OpenShift Origin, as it's provides the flexibility, scalability and stability needed for an open access interface on the basis of openEO. A major challenge was the data management, as each job that is running in a pod, requires that the EODC data storage is mounted to access Sentinel data and furthermore to have the ability to write outputs to persistent storage. Since Sentinel data at EODC is hosted as compressed files (level 1c), the processing was challenging, as the extraction of the data can have major performance impacts. Finally, since each Sentinel product has another file structure, data extractors had to be implemented for each product.

Did the implementation of the openEO specification influence your overall system setup (if yes, how)?

OpenShift was set up, to provide a platform to deploy containers and provide facilities for processing. In the future openEO might have an influence of the setup, and permission management of the EODC storage.

What was the most challenging endpoint to implement yet?

The jobs endpoint, as it required to provide a solution to process jobs.

Did you face any challenges when switching from openEO API v0.0.2 to openEO API v0.3.0?

The most challenging struggle yet, was to restructure the process discovery as the process descriptions changed significantly (more complex) and a validator needed to be implemented for verifying the validity of the parameter inputs when creating a new process. The implementation of OpenID Connect was challenging as well.

Do you have any other comments or experiences implementing the openEO API, you want to share?

A.5. R Back-End / WWU

Name of your company

WWU

What software package is the back-end driver targeting (e.g. WCPS, GeoPySpark, ...)?

R's raster package / GDAL

What is the category of the back-end (file-based, mid-level, high-level)?

file-based

Are other back-end systems used to serve openEO requests and enable processing (e.g. rasdaman, Spark, CSW, GeoNetwork, ...)?

MapServer for OGC services, R UDF webservices (in development)

Which technologies are used to realize the openEO API endpoints (e.g. Python/flask, node.js/express, ...)?

R/plumber

Which data products (e.g. Sentinel-2) are available at the back-end?

small Sentinel-2 dataset (300px x 300px, from 2016-12-12 until 2017-08-29), small Landsat-7 NDVI dataset (1km x 1km, from 2003-08-06 until 2014-12-26)

Do you have a public endpoint (if yes: URL)?

no

Other comments...

Do you already start to implement v0.3.0 of the openEO API specification?

No

Which technologies did/will you use to implement EO data discovery?

data discovery was not considered yet

What processes (e.g. NDVI) does your back-end offer and how did/will you implement process discovery?

processes required for the POC, process discovery was not considered yet

How did/will you realize processing jobs at your back-end?

The JSON graph is parsed and the stated parameter are mapped onto the backends implementation of the processes. The processing is then done by invoking the function stack of nested calls.

How did/will you implement UDFs (e.g. using Docker containers)?

At the backend data is converted into appropriate data chunks. The data chunks are then serialized into JSON and send to a UDF webservice (UDF specification of S. Gebbert, see <https://github.com/Open-EO/openeo-udf>). The service will probably be written in R and due to the fact of being a REST-service in probably will be provided as a Docker container.

How did/will you realize interactive web services (e.g. WMS, TMS)?

Currently processed jobs have workspaces where the results are stored as output. We use MapServer in a separate Docker-Container and accessing the jobs data through a shared volume. MapServer config files will be created by calling the respective /service endpoints.

How did/will you implement user file management and user storage?

We provide up- and download functionalities as it was specified in API v0.0.2. Data will be stored on disk, which is also available in the Docker shared volume.

Do you already possess user authentication at the back-end? How did/will you realize openEO endpoints for user accounts and authentication?

We use Basic-Auth / Token-based authentication. First obtain the token by using /login and then the token needs to be sent with each HTTP request where authentication is required.

Do you have an existing solution for user credits and billing. How did/will you realize billing?

Currently there is not billing realized (reason: develop/test system)

What is the next endpoint that you will implement at your back-end?

Most of the functional endpoints are implemented (the following functionalities were omitted: search functions, pausing/canceling jobs). One open issue is accessing the job log over a websocket (/job/<job_id>/subscribe) a general guideline how to do that is currently investigated. Then the next big step will be that we need to implement the changes coming with API v0.3.0.

Other comments...

Did you experience any challenges when when implementing the openEO API at your back-end?

When it comes to UDF processing the data management is an issue, e.g. tiling strategies, creating subsets and / or slices, etc.) Due to the intention of being a test system the performance is also an issue.

Did the implementation of the openEO specification influence your overall system setup (if yes, how)?

Yes, the different functionalities that can be offered like services made it clear, that different software/systems might be needed to be incorporated like MapServer. Therefore we incorporated Docker and containerized some of the functionalities.

What was the most challenging endpoint to implement yet?

The "services" endpoint and "UDF".

Did you face any challenges when switching from openEO API v0.0.2 to openEO API v0.3.0?

Not yet started, but the overall functionalities remained similar, which means that most work will be extending database schemas and adapting the changes of the exchange objects (JSON).

Do you have any other comments or experiences implementing the openEO API, you want to share?

A.6. Sentinel Hub / Sinergise

Name of your company

Sinergise

What software package is the back-end driver targeting (e.g. WCPS, GeoPySpark, ...)?

Sentinel Hub

What is the category of the back-end (file-based, mid-level, high-level)?

mid-level

Are other back-end systems used to serve openEO requests and enable processing (e.g. rasdaman, Spark, CSW, GeoNetwork, ...)?

OpenSearch

Which technologies are used to realize the openEO API endpoints (e.g. Python/flask, node.js/express, ...)?

node.js

Which data products (e.g. Sentinel-2) are available at the back-end?

Sentinel-2 (with future plans for Sentinel-1, Sentinel-3, MODIS; Landsat 5, 7, 8; Sentinel 5p)

Do you have a public endpoint (if yes: URL)?

no

Other comments...

No

Do you already start to implement v0.3.0 of the openEO API specification?

No

Which technologies did/will you use to implement EO data discovery?

currently we're using OpenSearch; we're considering STAC interface. back-end uses Postgres/PostGIS

What processes (e.g. NDVI) does your back-end offer and how did/will you implement process discovery?

max_time, min_time, ND*I, filter_daterange currently implemented; process discovery is in prototype phase right now, with JSON description of processes in node.js source code. We will probably keep this, but separate processes into their own source files (one file per process)

How did/will you realize processing jobs at your back-end?

The idea is to forwarding any processing jobs to the Sentinel Hub platform and let it realize the

job. The openEO driver will translate openEO process definitions into Sentinel Hub processing scripts

How did/will you implement UDFs (e.g. using Docker containers)?

We plan to support JavaScript UDFs, which will be embedded into Sentinel Hub processing scripts on the fly

How did/will you realize interactive web services (e.g. WMS, TMS)?

We created a simple node.js OGC web service which serves as an openEO-aware proxy to the equivalent Sentinel Hub services

How did/will you implement user file management and user storage?

We have not yet done that. When we implement this, we will use the simplest option available (probably some cloud database for structured data about users and source code; AWS S3 object storage for large files)

Do you already possess user authentication at the back-end? How did/will you realize openEO endpoints for user accounts and authentication?

Sentinel Hub already has an OAuth-2.0 authentication mechanism. If we do support authentication on the openEO interface, we will implement the appropriate bindings.

Do you have an existing solution for user credits and billing. How did/will you realize billing?

We don't. When we do, we'll probably extend our existing auditing and logging mechanisms (we already keep track and log users requests with the API Key and/or OAuth session identifiers)

What is the next endpoint that you will implement at your back-end?

support for long-running jobs

Other comments...

Did you experience any challenges when when implementing the openEO API at your back-end?

1) a major challenge was the need to have a stateful server, with storage of user data. (the API would have been much easier to support if it was essentially stateless).

2) another difficult aspect was the need to execute arbitrary flows, while the Sentinel Hub platform has a somewhat more rigid order of execution (filter scenes / create timeseries / evaluate algorithm on each pixel)

3) the interface for retrieving data from the service was a bit ambiguous and in the end non-trivial: WCS / WMS / TMS all return binary encoded rasters (images), with encoding typically specified by the client at the point of retrieval / openEO deals primarily with measured physical values, and does not clearly define the type of encoding of the result into the output image

Did the implementation of the openEO specification influence your overall system setup (if yes, how)?

Not yet, but it might influence our design decisions for the future

What was the most challenging endpoint to implement yet?

WCS (because it does all the work - all other endpoints basically just store data)

Did you face any challenges when switching from openEO API v0.0.2 to openEO API

D14: Back-end driver variability

v0.3.0?

We haven't switched yet

Do you have any other comments or experiences implementing the openEO API, you want to share?

A.7. WC(P)S / EURAC Research

Name of your company

Eurac Research

What software package is the back-end driver targeting (e.g. WCPS, GeoPySpark, ...)?

WC(P)S

What is the category of the back-end (file-based, mid-level, high-level)?

high-level

Are other back-end systems used to serve openEO requests and enable processing (e.g. rasdaman, Spark, CSW, GeoNetwork, ...)?

rasdaman is exposing the WMS, WCS and WCPS services

Which technologies are used to realize the openEO API endpoints (e.g. Python/flask, node.js/express, ...)?

Java

Which data products (e.g. Sentinel-2) are available at the back-end?

Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 and MODIS over the european alps

Do you have a public endpoint (if yes: URL)?

http://saocompute.eurac.edu/openEO_WCPS_Driver/

Other comments...

Do you already start to implement v0.3.0 of the openEO API specification?

Yes

Which technologies did/will you use to implement EO data discovery?

currently geonetwork with it's internal API's, in the future maybe STAC

What processes (e.g. NDVI) does your back-end offer and how did/will you implement process discovery?

all the ones from the proof of concept use case 1, in the future everything that is possible within the WCPS specification

How did/will you realize processing jobs at your back-end?

so far an internal database persistently stores jobs and execute them upon request with the corresponding jobid

How did/will you implement UDFs (e.g. using Docker containers)?

we are looking into several ways including a setup like in the OGC testbed 13/14 specifications.

How did/will you realize interactive web services (e.g. WMS, TMS)?

D14: Back-end driver variability

so fare using geoserver and rasdaman

How did/will you implement user file management and user storage?

not currently planned

Do you already possess user authentication at the back-end? How did/will you realize openEO endpoints for user accounts and authentication?

No, solutions not yet defined

Do you have an existing solution for user credits and billing. How did/will you realize billing?

No

What is the next endpoint that you will implement at your back-end?

data discovery

Other comments...

Did you experience any challenges when when implementing the openEO API at your back-end?

No

Did the implementation of the openEO specification influence your overall system setup (if yes, how)?

No

What was the most challenging endpoint to implement yet?

process

Did you face any challenges when switching from openEO API v0.0.2 to openEO API v0.3.0?

Not yet completed

Do you have any other comments or experiences implementing the openEO API, you want to share?

